

SOCIAL SCIENCES

EMPLOYING THE CHARACTERISTICS OF A STRATEGIC THINKER IN THE QUALITY OF ORGANIZATIONAL IMPROVISATION

Shuaib Mohammed Sharif

Al-Qalam University College, Iraq

ORCID:0000-0002-7662-1511

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6912884>

Abstract

The study aims to determine the impact statement strategic thinker specifications and its impact on the quality of organizational improvisation with academic leaders in a selected sample of Iraqi universities who represent the top of the educational pyramid of the administrative, scientific, The study centered problem that employ intellectual developments of strategic management in educational organizations will add a new enablers pay about the need for a specification leadership of the minds and behavior trends and frameworks thinking strategy that combines conscious assimilation of the field and the possibility of the application, And it adopted the scheme Default study identified through which the objectives of the study and its hypotheses and the researcher used the descriptive analytical approach in order to attain results, and form questionnaire as a key instrument in the data and information on the field side of the study, collection, and was selected three universities (University of Tikrit, Kirkuk University, Samarra University) field to study and test hypotheses, it was the views of a poll (80) leader academically.

The study has come out with a number of recommendations and proposals for universities study population consisted of the most important, that the surveyed universities management bother the results of the relationship between the variables of the study and the reflection of this relationship on the nature of their work, as well as to change the negative perception of improvisation organization for being in accordance with complementary to the planning and is not a substitute for it.

Keywords: strategic thinker, the quality of organizational improvisation , Vision, intelligence, academic leaders, strategic management, educational organizations, specification leadership, strategic role, strategic thinking.

Introduction

Organizations face changing circumstances and work in volatile conditions and are encountered by obstacles and challenges that make achieving the goals for which they were established is uncertain. On the other hand, the conditions, capabilities and capabilities of these organizations and the resources available to them and the pressures they are subject to stemming from their internal conditions vary. All this reduces the possibility of organizations being able to achieve their goals and achieve satisfactory rates of effectiveness by applying what they are accustomed to from traditional practices.

At the level of educational institutions, the tasks entrusted to the leadership position in educational institutions in the context of developments and changes in the environment, especially in the field of information, communication and change, and the multi-purpose and multi-dimensional challenges it has added, require re-considering the construction of the leadership's academic work tasks and containing its contents and ambitions, and related issues. Peculiarities in the specifications and characteristics of strategic minds to make the leadership position a site for making strategic decisions instead of getting caught up in the daily (operational) work details.

In light of these data, the intellectual framework of this study is centered on diagnosing the specifications and behavior of the strategic thinker and its role in the quality of organizational improvisation. It represents

the top of the educational pyramid from an administrative point of view.

Study Methodology

The problem of the study:

Within the framework of what was mentioned, the study believes that employing the intellectual developments of strategic management in educational organizations will add new capabilities that push towards the necessity of having specifications for leadership minds and behaviors with strategic directions and frameworks of thinking that combine conscious understanding of the field and the possibility of application, to form awareness and guide behavior and decisions, and then determine priorities and patterns of dealing With the environment for everything that is new and surprising due to unexpected or unplanned circumstances, by adopting improvisation and making important decisions at the time of realizing the event based on the available resources.

From this point of view, the intellectual framework of this study is centered through diagnosing the specifications of the strategic thinker in educational organizations and their role in the quality of organizational improvisation.

1) Do academic leaders in the study sample have a perception of the characteristics and dimensions of the strategic thinker?

2) What is the nature of the prevailing the quality of organizational improvisation in the educational institutions of the study sample?

3) Is there a relationship between the specifications of the strategic thinker and the quality of organizational improvisation in educational organizations?

4) Are the results of the relationship between the specifications of the strategic thinker a source of the quality of organizational improvisation?

5) Do the different specifications and behavior patterns of academic leaders have a significant impact on the adoption of the quality of organizational improvisation in educational institutions.

The importance of the study:

The study derives its importance from the importance of the topic it deals with and the location chosen for the study, where this study contributes.

▪ **Academic level:** The importance of studying academically is embodied in building a knowledge framework for the topics (specifications of the strategic thinker and the quality of organizational improvisation), as well as enriching and enriching the Iraqi library due to the limited studies related to the variables of the study, so the researcher seeks to provide an intellectual framework that is the starting point for other researchers to enrich this topic.

▪ **Field level:** The field importance of the study topic is reflected in:

1) Determining the specifications of the strategic mind of the academic leaders in the organizations under study.

2) The study of the independent variable (the specifications of the strategic thinker) and its impact leads to the possibility of determining the required level of support for these variables that positively affect the dependent variable (the quality of organizational improvisation) for educational organizations.

3) This study is important at the field level, as it will provide an information base that can be employed in the researched organizations, and this information will guide how to employ the characteristics of the strategic thinker that support the behavior of the leader to

add new possibilities in the leadership's ability to the quality of organizational improvisation.

Objectives of the study: In light of the problem of the current study and the lack of studies linking the variables investigated, the main objective of the study is to determine the specifications of the strategic thinker and their impact on the quality of organizational improvisation in educational institutions.

1) Develop a diagnostic framework for the specifications of the strategic thinker in the field of higher education, and the related capabilities that enhance the academic leadership position.

2) Presenting ways of paying attention to the specifications of the strategic thinker and their role in the field of the quality of organizational improvisation in educational institutions, as the level of awareness, diagnosis and response is the result of the interaction between the specifications of the strategic thinker for leadership, and in light of them, the data of the quality of organizational improvisation is determined as a tool that enables the academic leadership to take important decisions in record time and time Awareness of the event to improve performance and distinction compared to competitors.

3) Report of the academic community's perceptions of the general content of the assumptions from which the study was launched in the field of the specifications of the strategic thinker and their role in the field of the quality of organizational improvisation for educational institutions.

Study scheme: The systematic treatment of the study problem, according to its theoretical framework and field contents, requires building a hypothetical scheme that reflects the nature of the logical relationship between the variables investigated, as well as clarifying the sub-variables of those variables and their effects on the educational institutions under study, taking into account the possibility of measuring these variables and assuming that the relationship is one way.

Figure (1) .The hypothetical study scheme

Study Hypotheses: A set of hypotheses were determined based on the scheme in order to prove the statistical relationship and its branches.

✓ There is a significant correlation relationship between the specifications of the strategic thinker for the leaders of the surveyed organizations in terms of their variables and the quality of organizational improvisation.

✓ There is a significant influence relationship between the specifications of the strategic thinker for the leaders of the organizations surveyed in terms of their variables and the quality of organizational improvisation.

✓ The characteristics of the strategic thinker for the leaders of educational organizations in terms of

their variables and the quality of organizational improvisation in educational organizations vary in the study sample

Study Tools

A. **Data collection methods:** In order to achieve the objectives of the study and test its hypotheses, two types of data collection methods were adopted by:

1. The first type is related to covering the theoretical aspect through many sources represented by scientific references such as books, magazines, studies, theses and periodicals, available in libraries, as well as by relying on the international communications network (Internet).

2. As for the second type of data, it was obtained through the field study, and through the questionnaire form. It is the main tool in collecting data and infor-

mation for the study, whose formulation took into account its ability to diagnose and measure the main and sub-variables of the study.

It included the questionnaire in its final form and after making adjustments to the Its initial form is two-axis:

- It includes a paragraph of personal and functional information for the study sample that pertains to (scientific qualification, scientific title, administrative position, service in the position, university service).
- the questionnaire included two main variables: (specifications of the strategic thinker and the quality of organizational improvisation), as each of these variables includes a set of sub-variables shown in Table (1), which represents the structure of the questionnaire.

Table 1

Structure of the questionnaire

N.	main variables	sub-variables	number of paragraphs	Paragraph
1	Personal information	Academic qualification, title, administrative position, service in the position, university service	5	1-5
2	Characteristics of the thinker	strategic vision	10	1-10
		Strategic thinking	10	11-20
		Strategic Intelligence	10	21-30
3	The quality of organizational improvisation	Internal Resources	12	31-42
		Implicit and Cognitive Capabilities	12	43-54

The study questionnaire, with its approved standards, was subjected to tests of validity and reliability

B. Statistical methods used in the analysis

A set of statistical tools were used, including those related to the description of the study variables, and other analytical tools, as follows:

1. Descriptive statistical tools, which are: percentages, mean, and standard deviation.
2. Analytical statistical tools, including the following: analysis of financial indicators, (F, T) test, simple and multiple correlation, and simple and multiple linear regression.

Description of the study sample universities and the justifications for selection

Determining the sector in which the study is conducted is of great importance, and the process of choosing the field of study is one of the most important axes in scientific research, as the appropriate and appropriate selection of the field of study contributes greatly to the validity of the results and the testing of hypotheses, and through the theoretical and field vision in the organizations, the study sees That there is a need to inculcate the concepts of the specifications of the strategic thinker and patterns of behavior among academic leaders and what leads to the quality of organizational improvisa-

tion in educational organizations, and based on the foregoing, the justifications for choosing the field of study are determined as follows:

- 1) Harmony of the nature and objectives of the study with the reality of educational organizations (universities), with regard to scientific and leadership activity.
- 2) Educational organizations (universities) have leadership mentalities represented by academic leaders who have the ability to present innovative ideas, innovations, research and consultancy, and this is consistent with the nature of academic leadership work.
- 3) The cooperation shown by educational organizations (universities), and their support for us in obtaining the necessary information for study.
- 4) The importance of the role played by educational organizations (universities) in the intellectual, cognitive and social construction of the society in which they operate, and as the tributary to most organizations and the rest of the community circles with qualified scientific and practical staff.

For the purposes of this study, a sample of Iraqi universities was selected as an applied field of study, represented by (Tikrit University, Kirkuk University, and Samarra University), and table (2) shows a brief introduction to the study sample organizations.

The study sample organizations

N No	universities sample study	Date of Establishment	number of colleges	number of teaching staff	number of students
11	Tikrit	1987	22	2040	24700
12	Kirkuk	2003	11	700	8500
23	Samarra	2012	5	200	4500

Source: Iraqi universities website

Theoretical framework

What is the concept of the strategic thinker (mind)?

The concept of strategy is one of the relatively recent concepts in the management literature, and it quickly gained exceptional importance in the business world today more than ever before, and perhaps the reason is due to the rapid environmental changes. The strategist is the one who searches for strategies in the event of an emergency and the absence of planning, as well as analyzes the information and presents it on a plate of gold to the senior management in order to use it in formulating the strategy and giving sufficient knowledge to the administrative manager to know what is going on around him from the events as well as doing strategic thinking for the creation of ideas. The new one is the one that develops the performance of organizations and makes them more able to achieve their goals.

It seems from the above that the term strategist is very vague and subject to different interpretations as much as strategic leadership itself, and many writers may use the term strategist and strategic leadership when they talk about the mind and strategic thinker. He moves in the available spaces without being closed (Al-Douri and Saleh, 2019:9).

From this point of view, and to identify who is the strategic thinker, we present the following some of the expressions described by some researchers:-

- The strategic thinker is seen as the leadership mindset responsible for actions that focus largely on defining the long-term orientation and strategic vision, communicating this vision to the relevant authorities, loyalty, and the necessary strength to realize and achieve this vision, and inspire others to move towards the direction it is actually intended. Or the correct behavior :
- A strategic thinker is someone who has the ability to share, has a vision, maintains flexibility, has strategic thinking, and works with others to make change that builds a better future for the organization.
- Strategic thinkers use a shared vision to motivate people.
- What is distinguished by the strategic thinker is the high ability to identify deficiencies and untapped opportunities, formulate the ideal future vision for the organization, and express it well, and use unconventional means to achieve the vision and reach the goals (Al-Zoubi, 2012: 10).
- The strategic thinker needs additional specifications and capabilities, as he is responsible for developing the strategy and influencing others to follow it.

Importance And Role Of The Strategic Thinker

(Hill et al, 2016: 490) indicates that there is agreement in viewpoints regarding the importance and role of the strategist and his great responsibility in the success or failure of organizations. The traditional and orientation of the strategic role, which looks to the best horizon, and has the vision as a distinctive characteristic, strategic minds understand the meaning of events without being affected by their phenomena, and have the ability to make decisions quickly. In light of a changing and complex environment, the organization needs a leadership mentality of a new type with a strategic vision and possesses unconventional skills, capabilities and characteristics to overcome reality with a forward-looking vision to achieve the desired goals.

Hence, it calls for attention to strategic minds, because they are the category that is able to think strategically in their dealings with rapid changes and high-risk environments, and they are also able to envision the desired future for their organizations (Sosik and et al., 2015: 47).

Accordingly, the researcher believes that the importance of the strategic mind and the need for it is based on three main premises:

- The changing and complex nature of the environment.
- The nature of the competitive environment.
- The nature of leadership roles, capabilities and practices.

Intellectual Implications Of The Specifications Of The Strategic Thinker

The main and fundamental changes on the axes of strategic management and the developments and developments imposed by them in the course of the leadership roles and the frameworks of thinking that the strategic leadership must promote require specifications, capabilities and knowledge that are in harmony with the new processes of leadership work outside the traditional framework, these specifications represent crucial elements in formulating effective leadership and harnessing it as the basis for establishing the basic force for many strategic actions in any organization. :58), also referred to as leadership specifications as a set of behavioral and professional skills possessed by leaders working in organizations that enable them to achieve the goals set efficiently and effectively (Al-Qahtani, 2016: 143).

Extrapolating the nature of the characteristics that a strategic thinker should perform, makes us feel the importance and role of "mind" and the accumulation of experience and those characteristics that are difficult to have for many leaders in today's organizations. For the future? How do I meet the current selections? And how to support success and continuity on a larger scale, so the question remains, and the answer also justifies the

resort of the strategic mind, and even its need for vision, intelligence and strategic thinking.

There have been many empirical research and attempts that sought to identify and examine the specifications of the strategist as a leader and manager in organizations, but there is a discrepancy in the writers' and researchers' point of view in classifying these specifications that were put forward under the titles of features and characteristics and all that characterizes the thought and mind of leadership, and this is self-evident

due to their difference in Determining what those specifications are, and in general the management literature put forward a set of specifications for the mind or strategic thinker that the book addressed from the angles of their different interests and specializations, but they all revolve around convergent axes, the researcher tries to review some of them and we show them through Table (3) according to the chronological sequence With the selection of specifications to be adopted in the current study.

Table 3

Specifications of the strategic thinker from the point of view of a number of researchers

№	Researcher	Specifications
1	Al-Naimi, 2013	Strategic vision, strategic thinking, strategic decision
2	White, Colin, 2014	Macro vision and systems thinking, focus on intent or purpose, intelligent seizing of opportunities, real-time thinking, assumption-based thinking -
3	Darwish, 2016	Clarity of vision. High sense of the internal and external climate, initiative, flexibility and keeping pace with change, innovation, determination and perseverance, ability to motivate and build teams
4	Dess et al., 2014	Personal characteristics, intelligence, self-awareness and regulation, empathy, social skills
5	Peter, 2010	Accuracy and insight in evaluating future matters, ability to form a vision and formulate strategic goals, intellectual fluency, ability to interact with environmental conditions and variables, ability and ability to trade-off between strategic alternatives, ability to make strategic decisions

Based on that and in line with the objectives and hypotheses of the study, it has been classified for the purposes of the current study's methodology into three specifications (intelligence, vision and strategic thinking) to express the contents of the specifications of the strategic thinker in which organizations, including educational ones, participate, and occupy a large space in the practice of the administrations of those organizations

Strategic intelligence

The topic of leadership remains at the forefront of cognitive topics of interest to researchers and thinkers.

As organizations have begun to undoubtedly realize the importance of intelligence as a basic feature that must be characterized by the strategic minds leading organizations, and it plays a prominent role in deciphering the environmental complexity faced by organizations by providing the appropriate information at the right time, in addition to the diversity of sources of obtaining this information, so it will be more Accuracy and objectivity will lead to making right decisions that will enable the organization to know what is going on in the environment in which it operates, so the activity of these organizations will turn into a proactive activity, not reactive, and strategic intelligence is one of those entrances that lead organizations to success and achieve excellence in performance. (Al-Azzawi, 2018: 11).

From the foregoing, the intelligence represents one of the specifications and characteristics that characterize the leaders of organizations who enjoy and play a prominent role in upgrading the capabilities of the leaders of organizations, so it is possible to diagnose the aspects of the importance of strategic intelligence through the roles played by this type of intelligence that will strengthen the competitive position of the company

In addition to increasing its profits and gaining a competitive advantage through which it can achieve leadership and leadership over other organizations. The most prominent of these roles are determined through which the importance of strategic intelligence is manifested in the following aspects:

- The role of strategic intelligence in supporting decision-making.
- The role of strategic intelligence as a competitive weapon.
- The role of strategic intelligence in change processes.
- The role of strategic intelligence in resource allocation.

Strategic Thinking

Strategic thinking refers to the availability of the capabilities and skills necessary to practice the tasks of strategic management so as to provide the holder with the ability to examine and analyze the elements of the internal and external environment of the organization and make accurate predictions with the possibility of formulating strategies and making appropriate decisions at the required speed.

The importance of strategic thinking stems from the fact that it represents a contemporary approach to the study of strategic management and by means of which the goals that achieve the mission and goals of the organization can be achieved, in addition to being one of the most important real investments that help the organization to continue and survive. (Al-Salem, 2015: 54-60).

Use the strategic thinking method in organizations to gain a competitive advantage through which they can exploit opportunities and confront the threats they face by building episodic strategies, which is an important

tool for achieving excellence and success (Al-Khafaji, 2014: 74).

Strategic vision

The past events and experiences of previous studies confirm that the main aspect of the strategic thinker's specifications depends indisputably on having a comprehensive vision through which he can determine the direction of business as well as visualize what could happen in the future. That the vision is a work system that requires the leader of the organization to develop the ideal future picture, as well as to make everyone participate in the development of this vision in order to reach the change of work.

The vision was described in a variety of ways, as (Johnson & Scholes, 2014: 13) indicates that the strategic vision represents the desired future of the organization, and thus represents the ambitions or hopes in which the strategic thinker focuses all his interests and motivates the members of the organization around it, and sees (Tharwat, 2017: 96). The strategic vision is a mental image or a dream that the organization aspires to in the future, while (Al-Nasiri, 2013: 39) indicates that the strategic vision is the ideas, ambitions and hopes that the organization clearly draws and tries to aspire to in the future in line with changes in the internal and external environment.

The importance of vision for organizations is highlighted in the following areas (Ali, Al-Lami, 2015: 190), (Al-Ghalbi, Idris, 2015: 210):

- Determining the work that the organization is currently carrying out, through which it determines the needs that the organization is trying to satisfy for the customers and who are the customers that the organization is targeting and determining the culture that the organization uses in serving the target market.
- Determining the future strategic path of the organization, which discloses the extent of the development of the strategic vision, as it represents the creative thinking of the organization's management on how to prepare or prepare for the future.
- Communicate the vision to the lower levels and the workers in the organization in a clear way, to arouse enthusiasm among the workers and increase their understanding of the changes that occur in the business environment.

In light of what has been reviewed in these dimensions, we believe that the strategic thinker should collect, in addition to personal leadership specifications, strategic specifications, and thus become a strategic thinker who has foresight, insight, and a vision for the future, and is able to take appropriate decisions at the right time, and thus promote and develop the organization and achieve Excellence and superiority.

The quality of organizational improvisation The concept.

In recent years, the use of the concept of improvisation has increased within the modern concepts that the leadership mind should adopt and apply in its administrative work if it wants to achieve the goals for which it was established and to ensure its continuity and survival, (Masa'dah, 2013: 75), and despite the many attempts that It has been made in order to define the

concept of improvisation and clarify its features, dimensions, characteristics, methods, tools and challenges. However, the difference still exists among scholars in defining the concept of the quality of organizational improvisation:

- There are those who view the concept from the perspective of organization theory, as it is the ability of people to devise ingenious solutions to sudden, complex and unexpected problems.
- Others look at the concept from the perspective of the optimal use of time by making bold and correct decisions at the moment of the event that leads the organization to great successes, and whenever the time is very short and the improvised person is able to make decisions correctly, this is evidence of efficiency.
- There are those who view improvisation from the perspective of strategy as making decisions and adapting to needs and circumstances "changing" ideas that appear in new and innovative means that were not planned.
- There are those who look at improvisation from the perspective of organizational learning that it is objectivity rather than temporal convergence of planning and implementation" (Miner, & Moorman, 2012:2).

Through the foregoing, we find that both writers and researchers have defined the quality of organizational improvisation based on a specific intellectual background and accordingly we can conclude the following:

1. The quality of organizational improvisation is an intentional act carried out by the organization or one of its members as a result of the great pressures that pertain to the organization's current and future environment, and includes all parts of the organization, and involves making decisions that determine the future of the organization.
2. The quality of organizational improvisation represents a work that is improvised and of a dialectical nature that mixes a number of conflicting concepts such as mixing between planning and representation, between discipline and freedom, and between control and spontaneity.
3. The quality of organizational improvisation is the process of quickly realizing and understanding the event under time pressure and finding the appropriate solution for it according to the available current resources. In this sense, it represents an emergency strategy for confrontation with the aim of obtaining an advantage that enables the organization to improve its competitive position.
4. The quality of organizational improvisation The process of adopting intuition to guide work in a spontaneous manner according to its historical context, as a result of continuous changes in the internal and external environment, and this means that there is no time to allow for planning, and if the problem was delayed and not addressed simultaneously, the damage would have been greater.

Based on this, the study presents its procedural definition of the quality of organizational improvisation in line with the hypotheses and objectives of the current study: "Creativity at the moment of the event aims to

quickly address current and sudden crises through the deliberate integration of the formulation and implementation phase in order to produce everything that is new, so it is considered a complementary work to planning. It is not a substitute for it. In the event of inability to plan, improvisation appears to fill the gaps that occur in the organization's plan."

The importance of the quality of organizational improvisation

The quality of organizational improvisation is not a bad phenomenon except to the extent that it relates to chaos that leads to bad results. Rather, it is an effective tool through which organizations can confront crises and surprises facing the leaders of organizations when they are going through difficult circumstances and crises and under the influence of time pressure and the inability of planning to address these circumstances and crises. Turner, 2012: 10), so improvisation is a necessary necessity through which organizations can confront emergency crises, and organizations that did not improvise cannot face unexpected circumstances and disturbances, which made organizations forced to adapt and react quickly to events, and thus the quality of organizational improvisation became an important issue. For both organizations as well as researchers and scholars, this was confirmed by (kipkell, 2012: 3).

Dimensions and factors of the quality of organizational improvisation

In general, the management literature presented a set of dimensions and factors of the quality of organizational improvisation, which the writers dealt with from the angles of their different interests and specializations, but they all revolve around convergent axes. On (micro-structural procedural memory) because it does not determine if improvisation will occur or not, but rather it affects its extent and quality when it occurs and these factors are leadership, (information flow, characteristics of the improvisation, communication, resources), while study (Al-Anzi and Al-Saadi, 2017: 129) and (Al-Abdali, 2013: 100) the need for the quality of organizational improvisation to the pre-existence of a set of resources on which the improvised launch is based, namely (material, cognitive, emotional, social and cultural resources), and in the direction of Shamil (Al-Atwi, 2012:110) believes that some strategic managers invest in three theories in particular:

- Resource-based theory: it requires the organization to keep pace with the external environment with internal resources
- Capabilities-based theory: the organization must have a strategic position for itself within the market and use distinct capabilities to maintain this strategic position for the organization
- Capabilities-based theory: It links these theories above together through the exploitation of resources, renewal of capabilities, developing capabilities and creating critical capabilities.

Based on this and in line with the study's objectives and hypotheses, the dimensions and factors of the quality of organizational improvisation for the purposes of the current study's methodology have been classified into two axes (internal resources axis, and cognitive abilities axis):

a. Internal resources: which refers to the ability to organize and redirect resources towards certain areas, and includes basic aggregates (material, cognitive, emotional, social and cultural), as (Al-Saadi and Al-Anzi, 2017: 128) sees that improvisation requires a set of available resources. A person cannot improvise without knowing what resources are available to him so that he can carry out the process of improvisation and find an improvised solution to the emergency problem.

b. Cognitive capabilities Capabilities are complex packages of skills, knowledge and accumulated capabilities that help the organization to coordinate its activities and make the most of its resources in an optimal way to achieve success.

1. It is mentioned (Aldridge, 2014: 10) that capabilities are the ability of the organization's management to develop strategies based on sound foundations at a set of different levels, or it is the ability to apply and manage strategic thinking in response to changing environments, and to ensure the organization's capabilities to adapt to rapid changes and provide better performance.

In general, abilities are classified into three dimensions, which are perceptual abilities, learning abilities and integration abilities.

The theoretical relationship between the variables of the study

The term the quality of organizational improvisation has taken on a strategic character with the expansion of organizations' horizons and the development of their future directions to serve their strategic direction. The quality of organizational improvisation represents an emergency strategy in which the formulation phase disappears by implementation in the context of a common awareness of individual or collective performance, based on the implicit capabilities that automatically reveal themselves at the moment of improvisation. , which in this sense shows the organization's ability to respond to the trend of changes and changing situations, and this undoubtedly requires leadership abilities and cognitive abilities (Ojha, 2018:36), and in return, most researchers emphasized the basic characteristics of the strategic thinker (vision, intelligence and thinking) that should be Present in the personality of the strategic mind when improvising.

Based on the analysis of the philosophical content to promote the quality of organizational improvisation in educational organizations, it requires to a large extent the availability of specifications for the leadership mind and the transformation in patterns of behavior to help enable the educational organization to transform its vision into reality and achieve a better situation that leads to increased productivity and achievement of excellence and access to organizational effectiveness.

Describe and diagnose the study variables test their hypotheses

In order to identify the variables adopted in the study model and its hypotheses and the nature of the relationship and influence (for the impact of the specifications of the strategic thinker on the quality of organizational improvisation), and according to the answers of the research sample members to the questionnaire in

the selected universities (Tikrit University, Kirkuk University, Samarra University), which number (80) forms

Describing and diagnosing the dimensions of the specifications of the strategic thinker

It is clear from the percentages, arithmetic means, and standard deviations in Table (4) regarding the attitudes of the study sample (academic leaders) about the specifications of the strategic thinker, considering that the hypothetical mean equals (3) on the scale space, as the results indicate that the specifications of the strategic thinker at the macro level have He achieved an arithmetic mean of (4.17), which is a high level, and this indicates a good level in emphasizing the need for

academic leaders to have strategic specifications, and therefore we note that the standard deviation of (0.70) indicates that there is a small percentage of dispersion in the answers of the study sample, which means that they have a clear vision On the meaning of the required strategic specifications, and these percentages of agreement, neutral and disagreement are supported, amounting to (86.92, 10.21, 2.87), respectively, and one of the most prominent dimensions that contributed to enriching the specification variable is the strategic vision dimension with a percentage of agreement (90.25), an arithmetic mean of (4.28) and a deviation norm of (0.65)

Table 4

The attitudes of the study sample			
<i>Variable</i>	<i>Dimensions</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>St. Deviation</i>
strategic thinker	<i>Vision</i>	4.28	0.65
	<i>Intelligence</i>	4.20	0.69
	<i>Thinking</i>	4.04	0.77
Average		4.17	0.70

Describing and diagnosing the dimensions of the quality of organizational improvisation:

It is clear from the percentages, arithmetic means, and standard deviations in Table (5) regarding the attitudes of the study sample (academic leaders) about the dimensions of the quality of organizational improvisation, considering that the hypothetical mean equals (3) on the scale space, as the results indicate that the dimensions of the quality of organizational improvisation at the macro level have He achieved an arithmetic mean of (3.96), which is a good level, and we note that the standard deviation of (0.78) indicates that there is a

small percentage of dispersion in the answers of the study sample, which means that they have a clear perception of the meaning of the quality of organizational improvisation, and these percentages of agreement, neutral and disagreement are supported by (80.28, 14.43, 5.29) respectively.

Among the most prominent dimensions that contributed to enriching the specifications variable is the dimension of strategic internal resources with an agreement ratio of (84.16), an arithmetic mean of (4.04) and a standard deviation of (0.72).

Table 5

responses of the study sample on the dimensions of the quality of organizational improvisation			
<i>variable</i>	<i>Dimensions</i>	<i>mean</i>	<i>St. deviation</i>
the quality of organizational improvisation	internal resources	4.04	0.72
	implicit capabilities	3.87	0.83
Average		3.96	0.78

Study hypotheses test

Testing the first hypothesis: It indicates that there is a significant correlation between the specifications of the strategic thinker for the leaders of the universities in the study sample in terms of its variables and the quality of organizational improvisation.

Table (6) shows the validity of the first hypothesis test, which indicates the existence of a significant correlation between the specifications of the strategic thinker and the the quality of organizational improvisation of the leaders of the surveyed organizations at the total level in the universities surveyed, as the value of the correlation coefficient reached (0.537) at the level of significance (0.05), confirming what was highlighted by The study, in its theoretical aspect, on the impact of the specifications of the strategic thinker in the researched universities in the quality of organizational improvisation. This indicates the contribution of the characteristics of the strategic thinker, represented by strategic vision, strategic intelligence, and strategic

thinking, in achieving the quality of organizational improvisation in the universities surveyed. At the micro level, the results were:

Table (6) shows the measurement of the correlation relationship between the dimensions of the specifications of the strategic thinker and the quality of organizational improvisation to test the validity of the first hypothesis which indicates the existence of a significant correlation relationship between the specifications of the strategic thinker in terms of its dimensions (strategic vision, strategic intelligence, and strategic thinking) and the quality of organizational improvisation. The results reveal There is a significant correlation between the two variables, as the value of the correlation coefficient, arranged according to the dimensions, respectively (strategic vision, strategic intelligence, and strategic thinking), reached (0.464), (0.436) and (0.411), at a level of significance of 0.05), which is the value of It ranged from very good to relatively good.

These results indicate that the more leaders in the universities surveyed enjoy the characteristics of a strategic thinker, the more they are able to adopt the quality of organizational improvisation.

Table 6

The correlation relationship					average
Strategic thinker					
the quality of organizational improvisation	internal resources	Vision	intelligence	Thinking	0.519
		implicit capabilities	0.339	0.456	
		0.438	0.274	0.242	0.379
average		0.464	0.436	0.411	0.537

N=80 Sig=(0.05)

Table (7) shows the results of measuring the correlation relationship between the specifications of the strategic thinker and the quality of organizational improvisation at the level of each university. Correlation

at the University of Samarra (0.708), at the University of Kirkuk (0.496), and at the University of Tikrit (0.444), respectively, at a significant level of 0.05

Table 7

Correlation relations at the level of each university			
Correlation Coefficient	N	University	-
0.444	43	Tikrit	1
0.496	22	Kirkuk	2
0.708	15	Samarra	3

N=80 Sig=(0.05)

We conclude from the preceding that all of the test results for the correlation between strategic thinker specifications and the quality of organizational improvisation at the macro and university levels were positive and moral, ranging from good to very good to excellent, and thus we come to accept the hypothesis of the first study

Testing the second hypothesis: Based on the content of the hypothesis that indicates the existence of a significant influence relationship to the dimensions of the specifications of the strategic thinker in the quality of organizational improvisation at the macro level, at the level of dimensions, and at the level of each university, we present the test results as follows:

- **At the macro level:** the results indicate the existence of a significant influence relationship for the specifications of the strategic thinker in the quality of organizational improvisation, as the total of what the dimensions of the specifications of the strategic thinker explain in the the quality of organizational improvisation variable according to the value of (R2) amounted to about (29%), while (71%) of the change in the culture of excellence is attributed to other random variables that cannot be controlled or that they were not included in the regression model, and this is supported by the value of the regression coefficient (B1) of (0.537), which indicates that if the strategic thinker specifications variable increases by one unit The the quality of organizational improvisation variable will increase by (0.537), which is a significant increase according to the calculated (F) value, which amounted to (31.57) and is greater than its tabular value of (4.001) at two degrees of freedom (1.78) and within the level of significance (0.05), as well as According to the calculated (T) value of (5.61) which is greater than its tabular value of

(1.671) under the level of significance (0.05). These results show the importance of the specifications of the strategic thinker in the quality of organizational improvisation.

- **At the dimensional level,** the results indicate the following:

The impact of the strategic vision dimension on the quality of organizational improvisation. Table (8) shows that there is a significant effect relationship to the strategic vision dimension in the quality of organizational improvisation, as the total of what is explained by the strategic vision dimension in the quality of organizational improvisation according to the value of (R2) amounted to about (22%), while (78%) Of the change in the quality of organizational improvisation is attributed to other random variables that cannot be controlled or that they were not included in the regression model, and this is supported by the value of the regression coefficient (B1) of (0.464), which indicates that if the strategic vision increases by one unit, the the quality of organizational improvisation variable It will increase by (0.464) units, which is a significant increase according to the calculated (F) value, which amounted to (21.35), which is greater than its tabular value of (4.001) at two degrees of freedom (1.78) and within a significant level (0.05), as well as according to the value of (The calculated T of (4.62) which is greater than its tabular value of (1.671) under the level of significance (0.05), and these results illustrate the role of the strategic vision dimension in the quality of organizational improvisation.

The impact of the strategic intelligence dimension on the quality of organizational improvisation

Table (8) shows that there is a significant effect relationship for the dimension of strategic intelligence

in the quality of organizational improvisation, as the total of what is explained by the dimension of strategic intelligence in the quality of organizational improvisation according to the value of (R²) amounted to about (19%), while (81%) Of the change in the culture of excellence is attributed to other random variables that cannot be controlled or that they were not included in the regression model, and this is supported by the value of the regression coefficient (B₁) of (0.436), which indicates that if the strategic intelligence dimension increases by one unit, the the quality of organizational improvisation variable will increase By (0.436) units, which is a significant increase according to the calculated (F) value of (18.30), which is greater than its tabular value of (4.001) at two degrees of freedom (1.78) and within a significant level (0.05), as well as according to the value of (T.) calculated amounting to (4.27) which is greater than its tabular value of (1.671) under the level of significance (0.05), and these results illustrate the role of the strategic intelligence dimension in the quality of organizational improvisation.

The impact of strategic thinking on the quality of organizational improvisation.

Table (8) shows that there is a significant effect relationship for the dimension of strategic thinking in the quality of organizational improvisation, as the total of what is explained by the dimension of strategic thinking in the quality of organizational improvisation according to the value of (R²) amounted to about (17%), while (83%) Of the change in the culture of excellence is attributed to other random variables that cannot be controlled or that they were not included in the regression model, and this is supported by the value of the regression coefficient (B₁) of (0.411), which indicates that if it increases after strategic thinking by one unit, the variable of the quality of organizational improvisation It will increase by (0.411) units, which is a significant increase according to the calculated (F) value of (15.85), which is greater than its tabular value of (4.001) at two degrees of freedom (1.78) and within a significant level (0.05), as well as according to the value of (The calculated T of (3.98), which is greater than its tabular value of (1.671), is below the level of significance (0.05). These results illustrate the role of the strategic thinking dimension in the quality of organizational improvisation.

Table 8

results of the influence relationship between variables and dimensions

Ex. Variable Resp. variable	the quality of organizational improvisation				
	B ₀	B ₁	R ²	F	T
<i>strategic thinker</i>					
<i>strategic vision</i>	0.476	0.464	0.215	21.35	4.62
<i>strategic intelligence</i>	0.416	0.436	0.190	18.30	4.27
<i>strategic thinking</i>	0.424	0.411	0.169	15.85	3.98
<i>Dimensions combined</i>	0.428	0.537	0.288	31.57	5.61

*P ≤ 0.0 df

(1,78)

N= 80

It is clear to us from the above, that the most influential dimensions of the specifications of the strategic thinker in the quality of organizational improvisation is the strategic vision from the rest of the other explanatory dimensions, followed by strategic intelligence and then after strategic thinking finally

The third hypothesis test

Based on the content of the third hypothesis, which refers to the varying levels of influence of the specifications of the strategic thinker in the quality of organizational improvisation in the researched educational institutions, and in light of the results of table (9) we present the test results as follows: (R², which amounted to (0.501), as well as according to the value

of (T) calculated, which amounted to (3.61), while the University of Kirkuk came in second place, where the value of the coefficient of determination reached (R²), (0.246), as well as according to the value of (computed T) which amounted to (2.55), The University of Tikrit comes in third place with a coefficient of determination (R²) that amounted to about (0.197), and this is supported by the value of (T) calculated, which amounted to (3.17).

And the data of these results confirm the acceptance of the third hypothesis, which indicates the varying levels of influence of the specifications of the strategic thinker on the quality of organizational improvisation in the educational institutions studied.

Table 9

The results of the relationship of the impact of the specifications of the thinker in improvisation at the level of each university

Ex. Variable Resp. variable	the quality of organizational improvisation						
	University	N	B ₀	B ₁	R ²	F	T
<i>strategic thinker</i>	Tikrit	43	.335	0.444	0.197	10.04	3.17
	Kirkuk	22	0.532	0.496	0.246	6.51	2.55
	Samarra	15	0.504	0.708	0.501	13.03	3.61

*P ≤ 0.05

df (1,78)

N=80

CONCLUSIONS

To complement the study's methodology, the intellectual frameworks for its variables, and the results of the statistical analysis used in proportion to its limits and hypotheses, this axis is devoted to reviewing the most important results and recommendations made by the study, and through the following two paragraphs:-

The specifications of the strategic thinker are one of the most important requirements for initiating leadership work, but rather for choosing the leadership itself, which represents the solid ground upon which we can build a strategic personality capable of dealing with environmental developments successfully and with distinction.

These specifications are gaining in our changing world a great deal of importance, if we want our businesses to excel and our organizations to succeed and excel and to elevate their social responsibility, now or in the future. Therefore, the strategic minds who aspire to seize opportunities before others who have unimportant intellectual dimensions will prevail. It allows them to visualize, intuition, foresight, and perceive with the aim of penetrating the unknown and approximating the image of the future.

The quality of organizational improvisation is a bold step forward under complex environmental conditions that contribute to the development of administrative leaders and the generation of new and resulting experiences and makes these organizations more capable of achieving the goals for which they were established.

Improvisation is a complement to planning and not a substitute for it. When pre-prepared plans are unable to meet the challenges and ambiguous circumstances surrounding them, in this case the organization resorts to the quality of organizational improvisation and prepares it as an emergency strategy through which it can confront everything that is new and urgent.

Improvisation is not a bad phenomenon except as much as it relates to chaos that leads to bad results. Rather, it is an effective tool through which organizations can face crises and the surprise that faces the leaders of organizations when they are going through difficult circumstances and crises under the influence of time pressure and the inability of planning to address these conditions and crises.

The academic leaders of the study sample possess an understanding and awareness about the study variables, as the answers in general were very good, and the positive trend proves that the specifications of the strategic thinker support the adoption of the process of the quality of organizational improvisation.

The results of the variable of the quality of organizational improvisation and the significance of its dimensions showed that academic leaders in universities have a clear vision of the process of improvisation, and the internal resources dimension ranked first with a rate of (84.16%), which is a very good percentage, then came after implicit capabilities in the second place with a rate of (76.4%). .

The results showed that there is a significant correlation relationship between the specifications of the strategic thinker for the leaders of the surveyed organi-

zations in terms of their variables and the quality of organizational improvisation according to the value of the correlation coefficient at the macro and micro levels. Followed by strategic intelligence, and then after strategic thinking. As for measuring the correlation relationship at the level of universities according to the value of the correlation coefficient, Samarra University was in the first place, then Kirkuk University in the second place, while Tikrit University came in the third place.

The conclusions related to the statistical test confirm the validity of the sixth main hypothesis which states (there is a significant effect relationship to remove the specifications of the strategic thinker in the quality of organizational improvisation) according to the value of the regression coefficient and the (T) and (F) test. As for the results of measuring the influence relationship on The level of universities The sample of the study was Samarra University in the first place, then the University of Kirkuk in the second place, followed by the University of Tikrit.

RECOMMENDATIONS

If the results of the hypothesis testing that it is permissible to speak are an indication of the existence of a problem, the conclusions are an analysis and clarification of the causes of the problem, while the recommendations are a treatment for the problem, and the following study presents a set of recommendations that may be a modest contribution to providing a treatment prescription that can be guided by organizations The study sample to avoid the weaknesses in the dimensions of the study and to strengthen the strengths.

1. The management of the researched universities should be interested in the results of the relationship between the variables of the study and the reflection of this relationship on the nature of the work of the universities of the study sample. The study recommends the need to pay attention to these variables and give them more importance because of their great impact in determining the future of the organization and ensuring its survival, as well as trying to benefit from this connection in Drafting university plans and making the required changes.

2. Activating the the quality of organizational improvisation process system to employ the universities' practice of their roles in community service and everything related to scientific research, consultations, programs, training courses, awareness and education in order to improve the educational level and benefit from new experiences.

3. The university administration should realize beyond any doubt the importance of the role played by academic leaders in universities and the great responsibility placed upon them. Therefore, it must improve the selection of these leaders and conduct specialized development courses for them continuously in order to enhance their knowledge, experience, skills and develop their characteristics. Leadership to support successful organizational change that matches the future directions of these organizations.

4. Organizations that aspire to success and seek to change their negative view of the quality of organizational improvisation, as it is a complement to planning

and not a substitute for it. When previously prepared plans are unable to meet the challenges, organizations resort to the quality of organizational improvisation and consider it an effective tool that enables the leaders of organizations to overcome these difficulties and achieve success. It suggests the need to develop the ability of its employees to the quality of organizational improvisation, and considers it the only way to save these organizations from surprises

5. Since change has become an inevitable issue, and stability has become anomalies or anecdotes, the management of organizations must research the developments of strategic management in order to discover a new method for dealing with everything that is new and emergency. Ambiguity and complexity, and that organizations that do not practice the quality of organizational improvisation will remain captives to traditional plans, and that achieving the goals for which they were established has become a far cry.

6. Given the importance of the topic covered by the study and the great role that academic leaders play in universities, we find it necessary to apply this study to other production and service organizations to diagnose the impact of the specifications of the strategic thinker on the quality of organizational improvisation in a more comprehensive manner.

References:

1. Al-Zoubi, Muhammad Musa, 2012, The role of strategic leaders in the development of security and civil organizations in Syria, unpublished doctoral thesis, Naif University for Security Sciences, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, p. 45.
2. Al-Abdali, Dargham Hussein Abd, (2013), "Formulation of a systematic scheme for the impact of the personal characteristics of managers on strategic intelligence and the quality of organizational improvisation", an exploratory study of the opinions of a sample of managers of private companies in Najaf Governorate, Master's thesis, College of Administration and Economics - University of Kufa - Iraq .
3. Al-Azzawi, Bushra Jassim Muhammad, (2018), "The Impact of the Relationship Between Strategic Intelligence and Service Operations Decisions on Strategic Success", PhD thesis in Public Administration, University of Baghdad.
4. Al-Atwi, Muhannad Hamid, (2012), Core Capabilities and Entrepreneurial Marketing, Relationship and Impact, Master Thesis, College of Administration and Economics, University of Kufa.
5. Al-Nasiri, Wael Jassem Hamid, (2013), "The Role of the Dimensions of Strategic Orientation in Enhancing Administrative Creativity", an analytical study of the opinions of a sample of managers in the General Company for the Pharmaceutical Industry and Medical Appliances in Samarra, a master's thesis, College of Administration and Economics, University of Mosul.
6. Tharwat, Assem Abdel-Fattah, (2017), "The Principles and Basics of Strategic Planning, from the Strategic Planning Conference for Excellence and Excellence in the Governmental Sector", The Arab Journal of Administrative Development, Cairo, Egypt.
7. Ali, Muhammad and Al-Lami, Ghassan Qassem Daoud, (2015), "Analysis of the relationship between strategic vision and operational performance - an exploratory study in the General Company for Textile Industries," Al-Hilla, College of Administration and Economics, University of Karbala, Volume (3), Issue (9).
8. Al-Anazi, Saad, and Al-Saadi, Muayad, (2017) "The quality of organizational improvisation: A Contemporary Introduction to the Philosophy of Emergency Strategies", Journal of Administrative Studies, Volume (1), Number (3).
9. Al-Naimi, Salah Abdel-Qader, (2013), "Specifications of the Strategic Thinker in the Organization", The Arab Journal of Management, Volume Twenty-Third, Issue One - June.
10. Darwish, Abdul Karim Aboul Fotouh, (2016), "Strategic Leadership Characteristics", a scientific lecture at the Research Center, Sharjah Police: www.ship-olice.gov.aedownload, adspdfpress.
11. Al-Khafaji, Nima Abbas, (2014), "Strategic Management: Introduction, Concepts and Operations," Dar Al-Thaqafa Library for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
12. Al-Douri, Zakaria and Saleh, Ahmed Ali (2019), "Strategic Thought and its Implications for the Success of Business Organizations", 5st Edition, Al Yazurdi, for Publishing and Distribution (Amman).Al-Salem,
13. Muayyad Saeed, (2015), "The Basics of Strategic Management", 1st Edition, Dar Wael for Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan.
14. Al-Ghalbi, Taher Mohsen Mansour and Idris, Wael Muhammad Sobhi, (2015), "Strategic Management: An Integrated Methodological Perspective", 2nd Edition, Dar Wael for Printing and Publishing, Amman, Jordan.
15. Al-Qahtani, Salem Saeed Hassan, (2016), Administrative Leadership - Transformation towards a Scientific Leadership Model, 1st Edition, King Fahd National Library, Riyadh.
16. Assistant, Majed Abdul-Mahdi, (2013), "Strategic management: concepts - processes - applied cases," 1st floor, Dar Al-Maysara for Publishing, Distribution and Printing, Amman, Jordan.
17. Chang, H. R. & Hou, J. J. (2011). "Organizational change and dynamic capabilities; A case of high-tech company. Industrial Forum" 9 (1), 15-29.
18. Miner, A.S., Bassoff, P. and Moorman, C. (2012). "The quality of organizational improvisation and Learning: A field Study, Administrative Science Quarterly", 46 (2): 304-337.
19. Sosik .J.J., and et al , (2015), "Making All the Right Connections The Strategic Leadership of top Executives in High – Tech Organization", Organizational Dynamics,34 (1), 47-61
20. Turner,Freda,(2012), "when managers fail it is usually due to poor emotional intelligence". Journal of Applied psychology, vol 87 No 2, p304-311.
21. Aldridge, Stephen (2014)" strategy, strategic thinking and strategic capability" Presentation for the PF Leadership Forum 23rd May.

22. Dess, Gergory G. Lumpkin, G.T. & Eisner, Alan B., (2014), strategic management: creating competitive advantage, McGraw- Hill, 3rd ed, New York, USA.
23. Hill, Charles W. & Jones, G.R., (2016), Strategic management Theory: An Integrated Approach, 5th ed., Houghton Mifflin, Co.
24. Johnson, G., & Scholes, K., (2014), "Exploring Corporate Strategy: Text & Cases", Europe: 7th ed., prentice- Hall Inc.
25. Kipkelly, (2012), Leadership Agility: Using Improve to Build Critical Skills. UNC Business School. UNC Executive Development. PP.(6-8).
26. White, Colin (2014), "Strategic Management", Palgrave Macmillan, New York.
27. Peter, Lary, (2010), "Stratrgic thinking", Available from <http://www.Games>